

CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES WITH IN SITU GROWN CARBON NANOTUBES

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SUMMARY

An engineering material such as carbon fibre cloth has been exploited as a support for in situ growth of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and carbon nanofibres (CNFs) in order to produce the three-dimensional (3D) carbon nano-structures essential for development of composite materials for aerospace applications.

Keywords: Carbon nanotube composites, carbon nanotubes, carbon fibre cloth, CVD

INTRODUCTION

Three-dimensional carbon nano-structures with CNTs and less crystalline CNFs, essential for development of many applications, are still challenging from the synthesis perspective. Well known engineering materials such as carbon, ceramic or glass fibres could be exploited as a support for the formation of 3D nano-structures. Carbon nanotube - carbon fibre composite materials and 3D carbon nano-structures are increasingly important for aerospace and automotive applications. Growth of CNTs and CNFs on the surface of carbon fibres was first reported to improve composite shear strength [1, 2] and load transfer at the fibre/matrix interface [3]. The high surface area of carbon and ceramic fibres coated with nanotubes and nanofibres is important for use in electrochemical applications [4-6]. Jo et al. [7] reported excellent field emission properties of CNTs grown on the surface of carbon fibres in carbon cloth, which could potentially be used in flat panel displays. Boskovic et al. [8] reported low temperature DC PECVD synthesis of carbon nanofibres on the surface of carbon fibres using Co colloid catalyst. However, growth of CNTs on the carbon fibre surface could only have limited impact on the bulk properties due to the relatively small thickness of the CNT layer. In order to more efficiently fill the empty space between carbon fibres in the cloth with CNTs we developed a simple method using thermal CVD that is fully compatible with standard industrial C-C composites production process.

EXPERIMENTAL

A floating catalyst method, already optimised for CNT synthesis [9], has been used to create a dense 3D carbon structure within the volume of carbon fibre cloth. The nanotubes were grown at 760 °C and at feed rate of 1.2 ml/hour of a 9.6 wt% ferrocene in toluene solution. A mixture of Ar and 10% H₂ was used as the carrier gas and the

total gas flow rate was maintained at 750 ml/min. The first stage furnace was pre-heated at 200 °C to ensure that ferrocene in toluene solution is vaporised as it was injected. The second stage furnace, where nanotubes were grown for 2 hours was at 760 °C. Pyrazine (C₄H₂N₂) was also added to the solution of ferrocene in toluene in order to introduce nitrogen into the system and grow nitrogen doped carbon nanotubes. The nitrogen doped carbon nanotubes were grown at 760 °C using argon as a carrier gas.

The carbon nanotubes and nanofibres were also grown in-situ within carbon fibre cloth at temperatures around 750 °C using Ni powder catalyst (3-7 micron, Alfa Aesar) and natural gas in approximately 1 hour. Prior CNT/CNF growth carbon fibre cloth was impregnated with transition metal catalyst dispersion in alcohol or water. Carbon fibre cloth with in situ grown carbon nanotubes was assembled into a layered disc or block of desired size for further carbon infiltration using a standard chemical vapour infiltration (CVI) process. A solid carbon disk or block could be then machined to satisfy specific applications that would require exceptional material properties in extreme environments, such as aircraft or automotive brake discs, medical implants or plasma facing tiles in nuclear reactors. When carbon nanotubes were grown on carbon fibre surface nickel nitrate catalyst was used. The nickel-nitrate Ni(NO₃)₂ · 6H₂O (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.999% purity) catalyst were dispersed in methanol using an ultrasonic bath for 15 min. Carbon fibres (T300 3K 000 NT, Cytec Carbon Fibres LLC, Piedmont, SC, USA) and carbon fibre cloth (VCL N, Morgan Speciality Graphite, Fostoria, OH, USA) samples were dipped in this suspension and ultrasonicated for further 15 min. Dry samples were then placed in a horizontal tube furnace. Firstly, the samples were pre-treated in a hydrogen atmosphere at 500 °C. After temperature ramp-up to 760 °C, the nanotubes were grown on the surface of carbon fibres using methane and hydrogen gas mixture for one hour. The furnace was then switched off, filled with argon and left to cool down overnight.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Carbon fibre bundles, woven and non-woven carbon fibre cloth can be used as a three-dimensional scaffold for carbon nanotube synthesis on surface of carbon fibres and in the empty space between them. The use of a floating catalyst method with ferrocene in toluene solution resulted in CNT growth in an empty space between the carbon fibers in carbon fibre cloth (Fig. 1). When Ni powder catalyst was used the nanotubes/nanofibres are produced as agglomerates of 20-50 µm diameter. These agglomerates filled the space between carbon fibres. The amount of carbon nanomaterials produced was controlled using variation of catalyst loading. The nanotubes were approximately 10 to 20 µm long, and with diameters ranging from 10 to 100 nm. When nickel-nitrate was used, a uniform and dense CNT coating on the surface of carbon fibres was observed with average CNT diameter of 50 nm and length up to 10 µm (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. SEM images of carbon nanotubes grown on the carbon fibre cloth (VCL N, Morgan) using 9.6 wt% ferrocene in toluene in Ar flow: (a) CNT agglomerates between carbon fibres in the cloth, (b) enlarged surface of the CNT agglomerates showing individual carbon nanotubes.

Figure 2. SEM images of carbon nanotubes grown on the carbon fibre cloth (VCL N, Morgan) using nickel-nitrate catalyst and methane-hydrogen gas mixture: (a) a carbon fibre within the cloth with CNT coating, (b) enlarged view of the carbon fibre surface showing carbon nanotube coating.

The structure of the nanotubes and presence of the catalyst particles was analysed using transmission electron microscope. FEI Tecnai C20, operating at 200 kV, was used to obtain typical images of the pure carbon nanotubes (Fig. 3a) and nitrogen doped nanotubes (Fig. 3b). There are typical for CVD grown nanotubes kink defects visible on the low magnification images of pure carbon nanotubes and a layer of amorphous carbon visible on the high magnification insert. Also, there are metal particles (in this case iron) incorporated into the inner core of the nanotubes. In the case of nitrogen doped nanotubes their surface is usually smooth with a constant diameter. Unlike pure CNTs, which have iron particles encapsulated in the core, the inside of N-CNTs is free of metal particles. Instead there can be particles on the surface of the tubes, especially in longer synthesis runs and at both ends of the nanotube. The metal particles (dark spots) visible on the surface of the nanotubes are typically iron compounds.

Figure 3 TEM images of carbon nanotubes grown within the carbon fibre cloth (a) of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (b) multi-walled nitrogen doped carbon nanotubes

Another special feature of N-CNTs is that their inner core is not hollow as it is in pure CNTs, but is subdivided by discrete webs of single graphene layers across the bore (perpendicular to the tube axis). In the Fig. 3b the membranes in the middle of the tube are clearly visible. Careful analysis revealed that the multi-walled N-CNTs are build of concentric cones with very low conical angle (between 0.5 and 7 degrees) rather than concentric cylinders as in the case of multi-walled pure CNTs.

The nanotube samples were analysed using Ramascope-1000 system Raman microscope with the spectral resolution of 0.1 cm^{-1} and argon ion green laser with 514.5 nm wavelength. The level of imperfection of pure carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and nitrogen doped nanotubes (N-CNTs) was analysed based on the D (1350 cm^{-1}) to G peak (1580 cm^{-1}) ratio, where the D peak is indicating a disorder (presence of structural defects in the graphene structure) therefore in perfect graphite structure the I_D/I_G is zero. In the case of nitrogen doped nanotubes (N-CNTs) the D peak originates not only from structural defects but also from the heteroatomic composition of nanotubes, in this case the nitrogen incorporated into the graphene layers. The overlaid Raman spectra from CNTs and N-CNTs were shown in Fig. 4. The presence of nitrogen has been confirmed by the higher I_D/I_G in N-CNTs (Table 1).

Figure 4. Raman spectra taken from the pure carbon and nitrogen doped carbon nanotubes grown within the carbon fibre cloth

	I_D/I_G ratio	$I_{G'}/I_G$ ratio
Carbon nanotubes	0.42 ± 0.03	0.95 ± 0.21
Nitrogen doped nanotubes	0.70 ± 0.04	0.32 ± 0.08

Table 1. The intensity comparison of the D and G' peak for pure carbon nanotubes and nitrogen doped nanotubes grown within the carbon fibre cloth

In the case of G' peak (2700 cm^{-1}) an opposite effect has been observed of the $I_{G'}/I_G$ ratios (lower value for the nitrogen doped nanotubes) which is again typical for doping of nanotubes. Doping nanotubes with nitrogen is expected to particularly improve the electrical conductivity but also mechanical integrity due to the N-N interaction between the nanotubes.

It is possible to synthesized CNTs and CNFs by using a process in which the catalyst is impregnated and dispersed within the carbon fibre cloth. Boskovic [10] has found that when the catalyst is impregnated and dispersed within a fibrous matrix (carbon or ceramic fibre cloth or felt), rather than being left on the surface, a more efficient deposition of nanofibres and/or nanotubes results. A fine iron powder catalyst dispersed in iso-propanol was impregnated within carbon cloth (VCL N, Morgan Crucible Plc) using an ultrasonic bath. The samples were then dried producing a fibrous matrix with an impregnated finely dispersed metal powder. Carbon nanotubes and nanofibres were grown using an ethylene and hydrogen mixture at $650 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The nanotubes/nanofibres are

produced in clumps originating from the surface of the catalyst particles. The amount of carbon nanomaterials produced could be controlled using variation of catalyst loading.

Veedu et al. [11] reported that well-aligned CNTs grown perpendicular to 2D woven fabric of SiC fibres improved significantly the mechanical and thermal properties. Interlaminar fracture-toughness of the resulting 3D composite has shown an improvement of 348% compared with the base composite without CNTs. The interlaminar shear sliding fracture toughness was improved by about 54%. It is also reported that addition of carbon nanotubes has significantly improved the dissipation of vibrational energy under cyclic loading. The coefficient of thermal expansion was reduced to 38% of the original value and thermal conductivity was improved by 51%.

Three-dimensional composite materials containing CNTs or CNFs and carbon fibres are good candidate for many potential applications. High thermal conductivity of these materials may be of use in automotive and aerospace applications and for heat distribution or hot spot control. The high electrical conductivity of these materials could be used for example in electronic components packaging, as gas diffusion layers in fuel cells or in electromagnetic shielding. The carbon fabric impregnated with carbon nanotubes could be used for lightweight structures and for armour. The first attempts to develop carbon-carbon (C-C) composites containing carbon nanotubes have already been reported in the literature by Lim et al. [12] and Li et al. [13]. These C-C composites could be used for friction applications in aerospace and automotive industry and as a plasma facing tiles in nuclear industry. The carbon fabric impregnated with carbon nanotubes could be used for many applications such as lightweight structures, brake discs and bullet-proof vests. We optimized in situ CNT/CNF growth process for the production of C-C composite disc [14]. Carbon fibre cloth with in situ grown carbon nanotubes was assembled into a layered disc or block of desired size for further carbon infiltration using standard CVI process. A solid carbon disk or block was then machined to satisfy specific applications (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. C-C composite discs with in situ grown CNT/CNF produced at Meggitt Aircraft Braking Systems, Coventry, UK [14].

CONCLUSIONS

We have demonstrated use of carbon fibres bundles and non-woven carbon fibre cloth as a 3D scaffold for carbon nanotube synthesis on surface of carbon fibres and in the empty space between them. A mixture of ferrocene and toluene were pyrolysed over the cloth at the same temperature in order to grow the nanotubes in between the fibres. Growth of CNTs in the empty space between the carbon fibres could results in improvement of mechanical properties, thermal conductivity and electrical conductivity with potential for many applications especially in aerospace, energy and electrochemical industry. We also demonstrated a method of producing composites containing carbon nanotubes using CVD and CVI process. A transition metal catalyst was impregnated within the carbon fibre cloth prior to starting carbon nanotube growth in the furnace. Carbon fibre cloth with in situ grown carbon nanotubes was assembled into a layered disc or block of desired size for further carbon infiltration using standard CVI process. A solid carbon disk or block could be then machined to satisfy specific applications that would require exceptional material properties in extreme environments, such as aircraft or automotive brake discs, medical implants or plasma facing tiles in nuclear reactors.

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